

New non-zero gauge invariants outside an infinite solenoid

Alcides Garat¹

1. Instituto de Física, Facultad de Ciencias, Iguá 4225, esq. Mataojo, Montevideo, Uruguay.

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We are going to introduce a gedanken experiment by means of which we will prove the existence of new non-zero gauge invariants outside an infinite solenoid. To this end we will introduce a set of new tetrads that will unravel the relevance of electromagnetic potentials, electromagnetic field and new gauge invariants within the context of a unified geometric structure.

I. INTRODUCTION

In manuscript¹ a covariant method for the local diagonalization of the $U(1)$ electromagnetic stress-energy tensor was presented. At every point in a curved four dimensional Lorentzian spacetime a new tetrad was introduced for non-null electromagnetic fields such that this tetrad locally and covariantly diagonalizes the stress-energy tensor. At every point the timelike and one spacelike vectors generate a plane that we called blade one^{1,2}. The other two spacelike vectors generate a plane that we called blade two. These vectors are constructed with the local extremal field³, its dual, the very metric tensor and a pair of vector fields that represent a generic choice as long as the tetrad vectors do not become trivial. Let us display for the Abelian case the explicit expression for these vectors,

$$U^\alpha = \xi^{\alpha\lambda} \xi_{\rho\lambda} X^\rho / (\sqrt{-Q/2} \sqrt{X_\mu \xi^{\mu\sigma} \xi_{\nu\sigma} X^\nu}) \quad (1)$$

$$V^\alpha = \xi^{\alpha\lambda} X_\lambda / (\sqrt{X_\mu \xi^{\mu\sigma} \xi_{\nu\sigma} X^\nu}) \quad (2)$$

$$Z^\alpha = * \xi^{\alpha\lambda} Y_\lambda / (\sqrt{Y_\mu * \xi^{\mu\sigma} * \xi_{\nu\sigma} Y^\nu}) \quad (3)$$

$$W^\alpha = * \xi^{\alpha\lambda} * \xi_{\rho\lambda} Y^\rho / (\sqrt{-Q/2} \sqrt{Y_\mu * \xi^{\mu\sigma} * \xi_{\nu\sigma} Y^\nu}) . \quad (4)$$

We start by stating that at every point in spacetime there is a duality rotation by an angle $-\alpha$ that transforms a non-null electromagnetic field into an extremal field,

$$\xi_{\mu\nu} = e^{-*\alpha} f_{\mu\nu} = \cos(\alpha) f_{\mu\nu} - \sin(\alpha) * f_{\mu\nu}. \quad (5)$$

where $*f_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_{\mu\nu\sigma\tau} f^{\sigma\tau}$ is the dual tensor of $f_{\mu\nu}$. The local scalar α is known as the complexion of the electromagnetic field. It is a local gauge invariant quantity. Extremal fields are essentially electric fields and they satisfy,

$$\xi_{\mu\nu} * \xi^{\mu\nu} = 0 . \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) is a condition imposed on (5) and then the explicit expression for the complexion emerges $\tan(2\alpha) = -f_{\mu\nu} * f^{\mu\nu} / f_{\lambda\rho} f^{\lambda\rho}$. As antisymmetric fields in a four dimensional Lorentzian spacetime, the extremal fields also verify the identity,

$$\xi_{\mu\alpha} \xi^{\nu\alpha} - * \xi_{\mu\alpha} * \xi^{\nu\alpha} = \frac{1}{2} \delta_\mu^\nu Q , \quad (7)$$

where $Q = \xi_{\mu\nu} \xi^{\mu\nu} = -\sqrt{T_{\mu\nu} T^{\mu\nu}}$ according to equations (39) in³. Q is assumed not to be zero, because we are dealing with non-null electromagnetic fields. It can be proved that condition (6) and through the use of the general identity,

$$A_{\mu\alpha} B^{\nu\alpha} - *B_{\mu\alpha} *A^{\nu\alpha} = \frac{1}{2} \delta_{\mu}^{\nu} A_{\alpha\beta} B^{\alpha\beta} , \quad (8)$$

which is valid for every pair of antisymmetric tensors in a four-dimensional Lorentzian spacetime³, when applied to the case $A_{\mu\alpha} = \xi_{\mu\alpha}$ and $B^{\nu\alpha} = *\xi^{\nu\alpha}$ yields the equivalent condition,

$$\xi_{\alpha\mu} *\xi^{\mu\nu} = 0 , \quad (9)$$

which is equation (64) in³. The duality rotation given by equation (59) in³,

$$f_{\mu\nu} = \xi_{\mu\nu} \cos \alpha + *\xi_{\mu\nu} \sin \alpha , \quad (10)$$

allows us to express the stress-energy tensor in terms of the extremal field,

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \xi_{\mu\lambda} \xi_{\nu}^{\lambda} + *\xi_{\mu\lambda} *\xi_{\nu}^{\lambda} . \quad (11)$$

With all these elements it becomes trivial to prove that the tetrad^{4,5} (1-4) is orthonormal and diagonalizes the stress-energy tensor (11). We notice then that we still have to define the vectors X^{μ} and Y^{μ} . Let us introduce some names. The tetrad vectors have two essential components. For instance in vector U^{α} there are two main structures. First, the skeleton, in this case $\xi^{\alpha\lambda} \xi_{\rho\lambda}$, and second, the gauge vector X^{ρ} . These do not include the normalization factor $1/(\sqrt{-Q/2} \sqrt{X_{\mu} \xi^{\mu\sigma} \xi_{\nu\sigma} X^{\nu}})$. The gauge vectors it was proved in manuscript¹ could be anything that does not make the tetrad vectors trivial. That is, the tetrad (1-4) diagonalizes the stress-energy tensor for any non-trivial gauge vectors X^{μ} and Y^{μ} . It was therefore proved that we can make different choices for X^{μ} and Y^{μ} . In geometrodynamics, the Maxwell equations,

$$\begin{aligned} f^{\mu\nu}{}_{;\nu} &= 0 \\ *f^{\mu\nu}{}_{;\nu} &= 0 , \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

are telling us that two potential vector fields A_ν and $*A_\nu$ exist⁶,

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\mu\nu} &= A_{\nu;\mu} - A_{\mu;\nu} \\ *f_{\mu\nu} &= *A_{\nu;\mu} - *A_{\mu;\nu} . \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The symbol “;” stands for covariant derivative with respect to the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. We can define then, a tetrad,

$$U^\alpha = \xi^{\alpha\lambda} \xi_{\rho\lambda} A^\rho / (\sqrt{-Q/2} \sqrt{A_\mu \xi^{\mu\sigma} \xi_{\nu\sigma} A^\nu}) \quad (14)$$

$$V^\alpha = \xi^{\alpha\lambda} A_\lambda / (\sqrt{A_\mu \xi^{\mu\sigma} \xi_{\nu\sigma} A^\nu}) \quad (15)$$

$$Z^\alpha = *\xi^{\alpha\lambda} *A_\lambda / (\sqrt{*A_\mu * \xi^{\mu\sigma} * \xi_{\nu\sigma} * A^\nu}) \quad (16)$$

$$W^\alpha = *\xi^{\alpha\lambda} * \xi_{\rho\lambda} * A^\rho / (\sqrt{-Q/2} \sqrt{*A_\mu * \xi^{\mu\sigma} * \xi_{\nu\sigma} * A^\nu}) . \quad (17)$$

The four vectors (14-17) have the following algebraic properties,

$$-U^\alpha U_\alpha = V^\alpha V_\alpha = Z^\alpha Z_\alpha = W^\alpha W_\alpha = 1 . \quad (18)$$

Using the equations (7-9) it is simple to prove that (14-17) are orthogonal. When we make the transformation,

$$A_\alpha \rightarrow A_\alpha + \Lambda_{,\alpha} , \quad (19)$$

$f_{\mu\nu}$ remains invariant, and the transformation,

$$*A_\alpha \rightarrow *A_\alpha + *\Lambda_{,\alpha} , \quad (20)$$

leaves $*f_{\mu\nu}$ invariant, as long as the functions Λ and $*\Lambda$ are scalars. Schouten defined what he called, a two-bladed structure in a spacetime². These blades are the planes determined by the pairs (U^α, V^α) and (Z^α, W^α) . It was proved in¹ that the transformation (19) generates a “rotation” of the tetrad vectors (U^α, V^α) into $(\tilde{U}^\alpha, \tilde{V}^\alpha)$ such that these “rotated” vectors $(\tilde{U}^\alpha, \tilde{V}^\alpha)$ remain in the plane or blade one generated by (U^α, V^α) . It was also proved in¹ that

the transformation (20) generates a “rotation” of the tetrad vectors (Z^α, W^α) into $(\tilde{Z}^\alpha, \tilde{W}^\alpha)$ such that these “rotated” vectors $(\tilde{Z}^\alpha, \tilde{W}^\alpha)$ remain in the plane or blade two generated by (Z^α, W^α) . For the sake of simplicity we are going to assume that the transformation of the two vectors (U^α, V^α) on blade one, given in (14-15), by the “angle” ϕ is a proper transformation, that is, a boost. For discrete improper transformations the result follows the same lines¹. Therefore we can write the transformation generated by (19) as,

$$U_{(\phi)}^\alpha = \cosh(\phi) U^\alpha + \sinh(\phi) V^\alpha \quad (21)$$

$$V_{(\phi)}^\alpha = \sinh(\phi) U^\alpha + \cosh(\phi) V^\alpha . \quad (22)$$

The transformation generated by (20) of the two tetrad vectors (Z^α, W^α) on blade two, given in (16-17), by the “angle” φ , can be expressed as,

$$Z_{(\varphi)}^\alpha = \cos(\varphi) Z^\alpha - \sin(\varphi) W^\alpha \quad (23)$$

$$W_{(\varphi)}^\alpha = \sin(\varphi) Z^\alpha + \cos(\varphi) W^\alpha . \quad (24)$$

It is a simple exercise in algebra to see that the equalities $U_{(\phi)}^{[\alpha} V_{(\phi)}^{\beta]} = U^{[\alpha} V^{\beta]}$ and $Z_{(\varphi)}^{[\alpha} W_{(\varphi)}^{\beta]} = Z^{[\alpha} W^{\beta]}$ are true. These equalities are telling us that these antisymmetric tetrad objects are gauge invariant. We remind ourselves that it was proved in manuscript¹ that the group of local electromagnetic gauge transformations is isomorphic to the group LB1 of boosts plus discrete transformations on blade one, and independently to LB2, the group of spatial rotations on blade two. Equations (21-22) represent a local electromagnetic gauge transformation of the vectors (U^α, V^α) . Equations (23-24) represent a local electromagnetic gauge transformation of the vectors (Z^α, W^α) . Written in terms of these tetrad vectors, the electromagnetic field is,

$$f_{\alpha\beta} = -2 \sqrt{-Q/2} \cos \alpha U_{[\alpha} V_{\beta]} + 2 \sqrt{-Q/2} \sin \alpha Z_{[\alpha} W_{\beta]} . \quad (25)$$

Equation (25) represents maximum simplification in the expression of the electromagnetic field. The true degrees of freedom are the local scalars $\sqrt{-Q/2}$ and α . Local gauge invariance is manifested explicitly through the possibility of “rotating” through a scalar angle ϕ on blade one by a local gauge transformation (21-22) the tetrad vectors U^α and V^α , such that $U_{[\alpha} V_{\beta]}$

remains invariant¹. Analogous for discrete transformations on blade one. Similar analysis on blade two. A spatial “rotation” of the tetrad vectors Z^α and W^α through an “angle” φ as in (23-24), such that $Z_{[\alpha} W_{\beta]}$ remains invariant¹. All this formalism clearly provides a technique to maximally simplify the expression for the electromagnetic field strength. The new expression for the metric tensor is,

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = -U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta + Z_\alpha Z_\beta + W_\alpha W_\beta . \quad (26)$$

It is very simple to prove that $-U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta$ is a local gauge invariant under the local transformations (21-22), and by similar analysis $Z_\alpha Z_\beta + W_\alpha W_\beta$ is a local gauge invariant under (23-24). The stress-energy tensor can be written,

$$T_{\alpha\beta} = (Q/2) [-U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta - Z_\alpha Z_\beta - W_\alpha W_\beta] . \quad (27)$$

The tetrad vector U_α in expression (26) turns out to be the timelike vector just because we made assumptions along the way. On one hand we assumed that $Q < 0$, on the other hand we made assumptions like $A_\mu \xi^{\mu\sigma} \xi_{\nu\sigma} A^\nu > 0$. In our particular problem with the solenoid gedanken experiment it will turn out differently, for instance $Q > 0$ and the timelike vector will be W_α . Then, the invariants are $U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta$ and $Z_\alpha Z_\beta - W_\alpha W_\beta$. However, also in our particular case, the four vectors (14-17) will still diagonalize the stress-energy tensor (11). In section II we are going to find for the finite solenoid all the non-zero components for all the relevant objects, the electromagnetic tensor, the extremal tensor, the new tetrad, the stress-energy tensor and the new gauge invariant objects. In particular we use a metric with sign conventions $-+++$. The only difference in notation with³ will be that we will call our geometrized electromagnetic potential A^α , where $f_{\mu\nu} = A_{\nu;\mu} - A_{\mu;\nu}$ is the geometrized electromagnetic field $f_{\mu\nu} = (G^{1/2}/c^2) F_{\mu\nu}$.

II. THE NEW TETRADS IN THE SOLENOID SETTING

We are going in this section to apply all the techniques developed in section I in order to find the fundamental variables for the solenoid experiment. We proceed first for the case of a finite solenoid⁷ and then limits can be taken on different quantities like in the case of a long but finite solenoid⁸, and finally the infinite solenoid. We are not going to write explicit expressions for the components of the magnetic field since these can be found in

manuscript⁷ for instance, for the case of a finite solenoid which is our first approach. Therefore we introduce flat spacetime in cylindrical coordinates (t, ρ, θ, z) with a diagonal metric $(-1, 1, \rho^2, 1)$. According to manuscript⁷ the only non-zero components of the magnetic field and electromagnetic potential are B_ρ, B_z and A_θ . Therefore the only non-zero components of the electromagnetic tensor are $f_{\rho\theta} = B_z, f_{\theta z} = B_\rho$. If we call the determinant of the metric tensor $g = -\rho^2$, then $\sqrt{-g} = \rho$ and the alternating tensor would be $\epsilon_{\mu\nu\sigma\tau} = \rho \epsilon_{\mu\nu\sigma\tau}$ where $\epsilon_{t\rho\theta z} = 1$ and except for permutations all other components are zero. It is understood that even permutations of $\epsilon_{t\rho\theta z}$ are also equal to 1, odd are equal to -1 . Then, we find the only non-zero components of the dual to the electromagnetic tensor $*f_{t\rho} = \frac{B_\rho}{\rho}$ and $*f_{tz} = \frac{B_z}{\rho}$. Since the fields do not depend on time t we have or can consider only one non-zero component for the second electromagnetic potential $*A_t$. The complexion turns out to satisfy $\tan(2\alpha) = 0$ at all points and therefore, the extremal field is $\xi_{\mu\nu} = f_{\mu\nu}$. We proceed then to write the only non-zero components of the tetrad (14-17),

$$U^\theta = \frac{A^\theta}{\rho |A^\theta|} \quad (28)$$

$$V^\rho = \frac{B_z}{\sqrt{B_z^2 + B_\rho^2}} \frac{A^\theta}{|A^\theta|} \quad (29)$$

$$V^z = -\frac{B_\rho}{\sqrt{B_z^2 + B_\rho^2}} \frac{A^\theta}{|A^\theta|} \quad (30)$$

$$Z^\rho = \frac{B_\rho}{\sqrt{B_z^2 + B_\rho^2}} \frac{*A^t}{|*A^t|} \quad (31)$$

$$Z^z = \frac{B_z}{\sqrt{B_z^2 + B_\rho^2}} \frac{*A^t}{|*A^t|} \quad (32)$$

$$W^t = -\frac{*A^t}{|*A^t|}. \quad (33)$$

Next we are going to present the only non-zero components of the stress-energy tensor (11). We must remember that in our solenoid case the timelike vector is not U^α but W^α . Then, the local gauge invariants $U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta$ and $Z_\alpha Z_\beta - W_\alpha W_\beta$ determine that in our solenoid problem the expression for the stress-energy tensor compatible with (11) is $T_{\alpha\beta} = (Q/2) [U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta - Z_\alpha Z_\beta + W_\alpha W_\beta]$. We obtain then,

$$T^t_t = -\frac{(B_z^2 + B_\rho^2)}{\rho^2} \quad (34)$$

$$T^\rho{}_\rho = \frac{(B_z^2 - B_\rho^2)}{\rho^2} \quad (35)$$

$$T^\rho{}_z = -\frac{2 B_z B_\rho}{\rho^2} \quad (36)$$

$$T^\theta{}_\theta = \frac{(B_z^2 + B_\rho^2)}{\rho^2} \quad (37)$$

$$T^z{}_z = \frac{(B_\rho^2 - B_z^2)}{\rho^2} . \quad (38)$$

We can also write down the local scalar $Q = \frac{2(B_z^2 + B_\rho^2)}{\rho^2}$. Given the tetrad components (28-33) and the stress-energy components (34-38) it is a matter of algebra to prove that,

$$U^\theta T^\theta{}_\theta = \frac{Q}{2} U^\theta \quad (39)$$

$$V^\rho T^\rho{}_\rho + V^z T^\rho{}_z = \frac{Q}{2} V^\rho \quad (40)$$

$$V^\rho T^z{}_\rho + V^z T^z{}_z = \frac{Q}{2} V^z \quad (41)$$

$$Z^\rho T^\rho{}_\rho + Z^z T^\rho{}_z = -\frac{Q}{2} Z^\rho \quad (42)$$

$$Z^\rho T^z{}_\rho + Z^z T^z{}_z = -\frac{Q}{2} Z^z \quad (43)$$

$$W^t T^t{}_t = -\frac{Q}{2} W^t . \quad (44)$$

Indeed, equations (39-44) prove that the tetrad (14-17) diagonalizes the stress-energy tensor (11) in the solenoid case as we expected. Next, we must remember that in our solenoid case the timelike vector is not U^α but W^α . Keeping this in mind, then, the local gauge invariants $U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta$ and $Z_\alpha Z_\beta - W_\alpha W_\beta$ take as the only non-zero values,

$$U_\theta U_\theta + V_\theta V_\theta = \rho^2 \quad (45)$$

$$U_\rho U_\rho + V_\rho V_\rho = \frac{B_z^2}{(B_z^2 + B_\rho^2)} \quad (46)$$

$$U_z U_z + V_z V_z = \frac{B_\rho^2}{(B_z^2 + B_\rho^2)} \quad (47)$$

$$U_\rho U_z + V_\rho V_z = -\frac{B_\rho B_z}{(B_z^2 + B_\rho^2)} \quad (48)$$

$$Z_\rho Z_\rho - W_\rho W_\rho = \frac{B_\rho^2}{(B_z^2 + B_\rho^2)} \quad (49)$$

$$Z_z Z_z - W_z W_z = \frac{B_z^2}{(B_z^2 + B_\rho^2)} \quad (50)$$

$$Z_\rho Z_z - W_\rho W_z = \frac{B_\rho B_z}{(B_z^2 + B_\rho^2)} \quad (51)$$

$$Z_t Z_t - W_t W_t = -1 \quad (52)$$

Finally, the only non-zero components of the local gauge invariants $U_{[\alpha} V_{\beta]}$ and $Z_{[\alpha} W_{\beta]}$ are,

$$U_\theta V_z - U_z V_\theta = -\frac{\rho B_\rho}{\sqrt{B_z^2 + B_\rho^2}} \quad (53)$$

$$U_\theta V_\rho - U_\rho V_\theta = \frac{\rho B_z}{\sqrt{B_z^2 + B_\rho^2}} \quad (54)$$

$$Z_t W_\rho - Z_\rho W_t = \frac{B_\rho}{\sqrt{B_z^2 + B_\rho^2}} \quad (55)$$

$$Z_t W_z - Z_z W_t = \frac{B_z}{\sqrt{B_z^2 + B_\rho^2}}. \quad (56)$$

It is also worth noticing that we cannot build with the normalized tetrad vectors (14-17) any other local gauge antisymmetric invariant objects except for the two already introduced $U_{[\mu} V_{\nu]}$ and $Z_{[\mu} W_{\nu]}$. Finally, it is also evident that both objects $U_{[\mu} V_{\nu]}$ and $Z_{[\mu} W_{\nu]}$ lie at every point on orthogonal planes, that is, blade one and blade two, respectively.

III. CONCLUSIONS

We managed to introduce new local gauge invariants for general non-null electromagnetic fields. In particular, for the case of a finite solenoid we proved that these new gauge invariants take the form given by expressions (45-52) on one hand, and (53-56) on the other. If the limit is taken in order to get a finite but long solenoid, and this is the gedanken idea of this manuscript, in such a way as to satisfy the conditions given in paper⁸, then, it is simple to see that not all of the components of the invariants (45-52) or (53-56) are going to turn out zero. In fact, not even for an infinite solenoid all of the components of the invariants (45-52) or (53-56) are going to be zero inside or outside the solenoid. Therefore, we are proving the existence of non-zero geometrical objects other than the electromagnetic potential outside the solenoid. Now, we can also observe that not all of the tetrad components (28-33) are

going to be zero outside a finite but long solenoid⁸, or even outside an infinite solenoid. All of the four tetrad vectors (28-33) are going to keep a non-zero component for an infinite solenoid. Regarding the recovery of the electromagnetic potential vector from the tetrad vectors that diagonalize locally and covariantly the stress-energy tensor at every point in spacetime, we can notice the following. Let us consider the two eigenvectors of the stress-energy tensor,

$$V_{(a)}^\alpha = \xi^{\alpha\lambda} \xi_{\rho\lambda} A^\rho \quad (57)$$

$$V_{(b)}^\alpha = * \xi^{\alpha\lambda} * \xi_{\rho\lambda} A^\rho . \quad (58)$$

The first vector (57) is proportional to the normalized (14) while the second (58) is a combination of (16-17). Notice that the eigenvector (58) is gauged with A^ρ , not $*A^\rho$. Nonetheless, and because of its skeleton, it is inside blade two at every point in spacetime. The point is that taking the difference between both vectors and using the identity (7) we get,

$$V_{(a)}^\alpha - V_{(b)}^\alpha = \xi^{\alpha\lambda} \xi_{\rho\lambda} A^\rho - * \xi^{\alpha\lambda} * \xi_{\rho\lambda} A^\rho = \frac{1}{2} Q A^\alpha . \quad (59)$$

In our solenoid experiment the second term on the left-hand side in (59) is zero, while the first term is giving a potential vector with only one non-zero component given by,

$$V_{(1)}^\theta = \xi^{\theta\rho} \xi_{\theta\rho} A^\theta + \xi^{\theta z} \xi_{\theta z} A^\theta = \frac{1}{\rho^2} (B_z^2 + B_\rho^2) A^\theta = \frac{1}{2} Q A^\theta . \quad (60)$$

That is, the eigenvectors contain the information about the electromagnetic potential, which is evident by construction. We already know that for the holonomy of the connection^{9,10,11} this process of electromagnetic potential recovery or reconstruction is accomplished through an algorithm developed in manuscript¹². When we put together all the results above we realize that we have the new local gauge invariants $U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta$, $Z_\alpha Z_\beta - W_\alpha W_\beta$, $U_{[\alpha} V_{\beta]}$, $Z_{[\alpha} W_{\beta]}$, and the two local scalars Q and α . The electromagnetic field can be found through equation (25), the metric tensor for our particular solenoid case through the equation $g_{\alpha\beta} = U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta + Z_\alpha Z_\beta - W_\alpha W_\beta$. In a realistic

gedanken experiment we can assume the conditions given in manuscript⁸ for a long but finite solenoid. In this case the magnetic components are weak but non-zero, the tetrad vectors are non-zero, several of the components of the objects $U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta$, $Z_\alpha Z_\beta - W_\alpha W_\beta$ are non-zero, several of components of the objects $U_{[\alpha} V_{\beta]}$, $Z_{[\alpha} W_{\beta]}$ are non-zero, Q is non-zero and the electromagnetic potential is non-zero, all outside the solenoid. For an infinite ideal solenoid the tetrad vectors are non-zero, several of the components of the objects $U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta$, $Z_\alpha Z_\beta - W_\alpha W_\beta$ are non-zero, several of the object components $U_{[\alpha} V_{\beta]}$, $Z_{[\alpha} W_{\beta]}$ are non-zero and the electromagnetic potential is non-zero, all outside the solenoid. The fundamental result underlying all these constructions is the group isomorphism between the local groups $SO(2)$ and $SO(1,1)$ plus two kinds of discrete transformations proved in manuscript¹. We are not shuffling magnetic field components which are gauge invariant in order to get new gauge invariants. We are constructing objects like Q , α , $U_{[\alpha} V_{\beta]}$, $Z_{[\alpha} W_{\beta]}$ and $U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta$, $Z_\alpha Z_\beta - W_\alpha W_\beta$ whose fundamental nature can be seen in expressions $f_{\alpha\beta} = -2\sqrt{-Q/2} \cos \alpha U_{[\alpha} V_{\beta]} + 2\sqrt{-Q/2} \sin \alpha Z_{[\alpha} W_{\beta]}$ and $g_{\alpha\beta} = U_\alpha U_\beta + V_\alpha V_\beta + Z_\alpha Z_\beta - W_\alpha W_\beta$. These new local gauge invariants are not random assorted combinations of magnetic field components. These are fundamental geometric objects. We quote from¹³ "...in relativity, movement is continuous, causally determinate and well defined, while in quantum mechanics it is discontinuous, not causally determinate and not well defined. Each theory is committed to its own notions of essentially static and fragmentary modes of existence (relativity to that of separate events connectible by signals, and quantum mechanics to a well-defined quantum state). One thus sees that a new kind of theory is needed which drops these basic commitments and at most recovers some essential features of the older theories as abstract forms derived from a deeper reality in which what prevails is unbroken wholeness".

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